

Impact of regulatory advertisements in entertainment visual media on customer perception

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Abstract

The government and non-governmental organizations regularly take actions for the welfare of the community. In the past century, these actions were executed through newspapers and campaigns organized in different parts of the country. However, these campaigns had a small reach as the message of such campaigns was delivered through word of mouth. The advent of visual media in the entertainment world has changed this trend. In the modern times, the visual media has acted as an important instrument for calling on the citizens to act in best interest of the society. This is done through regulatory advertisements that are often delivered through the mode of television and social media. Further, these advertisements can also be seen before a movie in a cinema hall. In this regard, it is important to understand what customers perceive about such advertisements.

This study examines the impact of regulatory advertisements in entertainment visual media on customer perception. A survey analysis was carried out on 600 viewers of movies at different cinema halls in six states including Kerala, TN, Andhra, Telangana and Karnataka, and Maharashtra. The results indicate that those advertisements serve both advantages as well as disadvantages among the viewers' perception.

Key Words: *Advertisements, perceptions, regulatory, regression, encourage, consumers*

1) Introduction

Present day business organizations apply enormous efforts to design advertisements that attract the attention of their customers. However, the success of the advertisements depends on the media through which it is communicated or transmitted. Advertising companies try to target the channel of communication through which information can be conveyed to a large group potential customers. Before the 21st century, print media like newspapers, posters, and journals were widely used as the preferred medium of communication. However,

the introduction of electronic media led to the use of broadcast media deals including radio and television. It involves the placement of the product in the visual image in the program(Agarwal and Hosanagar, 2012).

On noticing the large scale impact of advertisements shown in visual media, government and non-government organizations (NGOs)started to display regulatory advertisements through visual media(Naveena, 2015). These advertisements are issued in favor of public interest and target the welfare of the citizens. The examples of some of the regulatory advertisements displayed in T.V and cinema halls include anti-smoking, anti-rash driving and national anthem. In addition to this, nowadays these advertisements are also displayed online on the youtube, Web TV and other visual media channel. The anti-smoking advertisement is framed with the purpose to provoke adult smokers to quit smoking. It tries to inculcate the belief that smoking is injurious to health. In addition to this, the advertisements are shown in the cinema hall to encourage the young generation to quit smoking(Singh, 2017). However, the impact of these advertisements depends on the behavior of society. Many times, these advertisements have been criticized on the grounds of unethical actions being displayed. Further, these advertisements are often time-consuming due to which consumers lose their interest (Natarajan, 2016). The national anthem practiced at the beginning of movies in the cinema hall is solely for the purpose of indulging patriotism among the citizens of the country. In addition to this, it is believed that national anthem builds loyalty and respect towards the country (Ravikumar, 2017). The anti-rash driving advertisement is shown for the purpose of creating awareness among the citizens to prevent accidents. This advertisement encourages people to follow the traffic rules. Further, the polio advertisements acted as an emotional appeal to the people (Mavoori, 2005). The purpose of the advertisement was to make people aware of those children under 5 years of age should be given a dose of polio drops. The aim was to make India ‘a polio-free country’. The government also headed various campaigns in this context. These advertisements were a huge success as high participation of the people was witnessed under the campaign (Mahra, 2013).

2) The aim of the paper

The aim of the study is to examine the impact of regulatory advertisements on entertainment visual media on customer perception.

3) Literature Review

a) Impact of advertising on consumer perception

The study conducted by Patel & Gaurav (2018) highlighted that it is difficult for companies to compete in terms of the functionality of the product. Companies try to influence consumer perception through visual images or video or through external communication. In this regard, advertisements act as a major instrument to support the sales of the product. It aims at creating awareness regarding the products and new market offering (Sumangala, 2015). It aims to generate liking and preference of the customers. Further, advertising tries to persuade the customer to purchase the product. In addition to this, the study highlighted that through the perception of an individual depends on the beliefs, expectations, attitude, needs, and expectations; the individual's response depends on the individual's sensation which is widely influenced by advertisement or brand name.

The value of the product depends on the perceived value of a product(Keser, 2011; Handriana and Wisandiko, 2017). A study conducted by Mandan, (2013)found that consumer behavior is widely influenced by visual images or videos that they watch on television or in movies. The customers usually develop a positive attitude towards the product or brand that displays attractive advertisements on the television. The satisfaction level of the customers depends upon the emotional responses obtained through product usage. These emotional usages are widely influenced by the advertisements(Mandan, 2013; Bhagat, 2017).

The advertisements that printed on newspapers and magazines have a smaller reach than the advertisements that are displayed in movies and television. In this regard, the study conducted by (Sharma, Bhosle and Chaudhary, 2012) highlighted that visual media advertisements offer greater benefits as they have the ability to communicate to the larger audience.

b) Advantages and Disadvantages of the Regulatory Advertisements

Regulatory advertisements have always played a major role in affecting an individual's perception in the context of social issues (Chaudhary, 2012; Bhagat, 2017). A study conducted by Mandan(2013) revealed that individuals often develop a positive feeling towards advertisements that attach social issues and develop

emotional attachments. Advertisements that make use of comparisons to deliver a sensitive message to the people will have a deep impact on their mind. There are multiple advertisements that make comparisons impact of smoking and nonsmoking on individuals' health. These advertisements show negative consequences of smoking and display the benefits of non-smoking (Vicker, 2015). Another important advantage of advertisements issued in favor of public interest builds confidence among the viewers as act as a mode of transfer of information. The new knowledge is transmitted to expand and differentiate from the existing knowledge. In addition to this, this involves swapping of the previous knowledge which was incorrect (Budiman, 2012).

The message developed through these advertisements tries to indulge a feeling of respect and brotherhood among the audience (Akhtar, 2013). In this regard, the study conducted by Hussain, Mcgarvey, Shahab, & Fruzzetti (2012) reveals that regulatory advertisements often create emotional appeal. In addition to this, polio advertisements show that any child can get the polio disease. These advertisements have negative consequences on the customer's perception. To this, the credibility of adults is capable enough to understand the regulatory advertisements to explain the motive of the advertisement.

The social message that is spread through media has a great impact all around the society. The study conducted by Sharma, Bhosle, & Chaudhary, (2012) highlighted that social advertisements play an important role in shaping the behavior and attitude of the society. These advertisements indirectly convince the viewers to break down their current undesired behavior. In addition to this, these advertisements are a mode to establish a desired behavior among society and stimulate the desired behavior towards the environment and their society (Nagaraj, 2007). For instance, the advertisements displaying the environment-friendly light bulbs make the user more environments friendly.

With regard to the disadvantages, the study conducted by (Hudák, Madleňák, and Brezániová, 2017) stated that regulatory advertisements are often time-consuming and are irritating and annoying. The customers who are aware and knowledgeable in the context of the information shown in advertisements often find them time-consuming or a waste of time. In addition to this, some advertisements provide knowledge regarding unethical

actions(Sidhu, 2015). For instance, the advertisement displaying ‘*Stop eve teasing*’ target to stop the unethical behavior but often display unethical actions are obscene and harm the moral standards.

4) Methodology and Discussion

Research methodology is a plan generated using scientific procedure applications to resolve a research issue in a systematic manner(Baxter *et al.*, 2008). The aim of the study is to examine the impact of regulatory advertisements in entertainment visual media on customer perception. For this, the researcher gathered quantitative data using the primary study approach using a survey analysis methodology. The quantitative data is collected from 600 viewers of movies at a cinema hall in six states including Kerala, TN, Andhra, Telangana, Karnataka and Maharashtra. The data was captured using structured and close-ended questionnaire. In addition to this, the researcher followed a descriptive and explanatory study approach. The descriptive study is used to evaluate the impact of regulatory advertisements on the customer’s perception. The explanatory study is used to identify the significant variables under the research study.

5) Data Analysis

a) Demographic Analysis

Figure 1: Demographic Analysis

Figure 1 above clearly indicates that majorly 54 % of the respondents were females and rests were males. In addition to this, majorly 39% of respondents were in the age group of the 21-30 years of age. In terms of educational qualifications, about 42 % of respondents were graduates. Further, about 40 % of respondents were self-employed. Lastly in terms of monthly income, about 50 % of respondents were earning less than 50,000. Overall, the sample was biased towards females. Most of the respondents were young, fairly educated and self-employed.

b) General background

Figure 2: General Background

Following this, the respondents were asked whether they paid attention to the advertisement displayed, the time duration for which such advertisements are displayed and the consistency with which such advertisements are shown on the visual media. In this regard, as shown in figure 2 above, 51 % respondents stated that the regulatory advertisements are displayed for about 1 -2 minutes. Further, 35 % strongly agreed with the view that they pay attention to regulatory advertisements of critical issues in the visual media. In terms of consistency of the advertisements shown on the visual media, 41 % agreed with the opinion that regulatory advertisements have shown consistency in terms of similar content shown in the visual media. Therefore, most of the respondents reported that regulatory advertisements are of short duration and viewed similar knowledge and thus did not capture much attention.

c) Inferential Analysis

The aim of the study is to examine the impact of regulatory advertisements in entertainment visual media on customer perception. Perennial to this aim, the researcher identified consumer’s perception as the dependent variable and the advantages and disadvantages offered by regulatory advertisements in entertainment visual

media as the independent variables. The researcher used correlation, ANOVA and regression analysis for the following proposed hypotheses.

Ho1: There is no significant impact of the advantages offered by regulatory advertisements on critical issues on the consumer perception.

Ho2: There is no significant impact of the disadvantages offered by regulatory advertisements on critical issues on consumer perception.

Perception on advantages offered by regulatory advertisements

Correlation Analysis

Ho1: There is no significant impact of the advantages offered by regulatory advertisements on critical issues on the consumer's perception.

Pearson's correlation was used to assess the relationship between the advantages offered by regulatory advertisements on critical issues and the consumer's perception. The correlation results indicate that there is a strong correlation among all the variables. However, the most strongly correlated variables are 'love, respect, and brotherhood (.863** sig at.000)'. This means that the message circulated via advertisements generates emotional feelings in terms of love, respect and brotherhood among consumers.

Regression Analysis

The table 2 in the appendix clearly indicates that the hypothesis i.e. impact of the advantages offered by regulatory advertisements on critical issues on the consumer's perception is rejected since the F value is significant at $p < 0.05$. In addition to this, the F value is quite high (320.718) so the probability for accepting the alternative hypothesis results to be quite high.

Further, the model summary presented in table 3 in the appendix indicates that R-square is 83 % and the adjusted R square is 82.8 %. So, it indicates that around only 82 % variation is contributed by independent

variables in the dependent variable. Therefore the model is good enough to explain the variation on consumer's perception.

Further, the regression analysis shown table 4 in the appendix indicates that all the variables except demographic values are significant at $p < 0.05$. However, out of all the significant variables '*Love, respect and brotherhood*' depicted a major impact on consumer's perception with the highest standardized beta coefficient of .665. This means that the feeling of love, respect, and brotherhood developed through the regulatory advertisements play an important role in affecting the customer's perception. In this context, the study conducted by Ravikumar (2017) highlighted that national anthem is played in the background music in a very attractive manner. The audience present in the cinema halls takes a standing position in order to respect the national anthem. The music played captures the attention of the audience and has certain intrinsic value. The audience develops a sense of love and respect for their country.

Also, '*Required actions to be taken*' viewed a negative impact on the customer's perception. This means that some of the regulatory advertisements display actions that negatively impact the consumer's perception. In this regard, the study conducted by Katherine Anne Montañó (2007) highlighted that some advertisements issued in public interest such as eve-teasing display actions to stop such activities. These advertisements often highlight that women are disrespected on their dressing that in turns creates an impact on the youth in terms of their confidence. These advertisements highlight that it is the responsibility of the citizens to take initiative to stop such activities. However, a large proportion of Indian society believes that women's modesty has a major impact on eve teasing.

Perception of the disadvantages offered by regulatory advertisements

Correlation Analysis

Ho2: There is no significant impact of the disadvantages offered by regulatory advertisements on critical issues on the consumer's perception.

The correlation results in table 5 in the appendix indicate that there is a strong correlation among all the variables. However, the most strongly correlated variable is ‘irritating/annoying’ (.771** sig at.000). This means that regulatory advertisements are irritating and annoying such that they are not able to enjoy the movie and is thus a major disadvantage affecting the customer’s perception.

Regression Analysis

The model summary presented in table 6 in the appendix present R-square (74.2%) and adjusted R square (73.8%). So, it indicates that around only 73 % variation is contributed by independent variables in the dependent variable. Therefore, the model is good to describe the variation in customer perception.

The table 7 in the appendix clearly indicates that the hypothesis i.e. there is no significant impact of the disadvantages offered by regulatory advertisements on critical issues on the consumer’s perception is rejected since the F value is significant at $p < 0.05$. In addition to this, the F value is quite high (212.222) so the probability for accepting the alternative hypothesis results to be quite high.

Further, the regression analysis shown in table 8 in the appendix indicates that all the variables except ‘demographic values’ are significant at $p < 0.05$. However, out of all the significant variables ‘*creates fear in visiting different places and making friends*’ depicted the major impact on the consumer perception with the highest standardized beta coefficient of .426. This means that the fear developed through regulatory advertisements have a major impact on the customer’s perception. Also, ‘*Incredibility*’ similar to the study of Akhtar, (2013) reflected a negative impact on customer perception. This means that regulatory advertisements deliver the message according to its aim and objectives

6) Results

	Results
<i>Ho1: There is no significant impact of the advantages offered by regulatory advertisements on critical issues on the consumer’s perception.</i>	Rejected

<i>Ho2: There is no significant impact of the disadvantages offered by regulatory advertisements on critical issues on the consumer's perception.</i>	Rejected
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7) Conclusion

The present decade witnesses many voluntary actions by the government and non-governmental organizations targeting social welfare. There is a growing presence of regulatory advertisements that can be viewed in cinema halls and television. In this regard, the present study examines the impact of regulatory advertisements in entertainment visual media on customer perception. Aforementioned analysis indicates that those advertisements serve both advantageous as well as disadvantages among the viewers. Few advertisements motivate the viewers to adopt ethical practices and few of them create a negative attitude in the customer's mind. Therefore, it can be said that the government should make effective strategies that must focus on educating and creating awareness among customers on working on its solutions rather than simply making them aware of the issues. Also, the advertisement information should be shared in a more creative manner that can affect the customer's emotional sentiments. This can be done using creative content with animated content. Also, the duration of this advertisement should be shortened but spreading a clear message and deep impact on consumer's perception. This study is useful as it highlights as the need on paying attention to this issue at hand since it captures a major segment of the population and has a much impact in respect to the desired change of attitude towards the world they dwell.

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Appendix

1. Correlation

		Do you think that there is any impact of regulatory advertisement of critical issues consumer's perception?
Awareness and Knowledge	Pearson Correlation	.732**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	600
Required actions to be taken	Pearson Correlation	.702**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	600
Entertainment	Pearson Correlation	.621**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	600
Credibility	Pearson Correlation	.616**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	600
Demographic values	Pearson Correlation	.622**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	600
Builds confidence	Pearson Correlation	.524**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	600
Patriotism	Pearson Correlation	.829**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	600
Love, respect and brotherhood	Pearson Correlation	.863**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	600
Updates on forthcoming projects and actions	Pearson Correlation	.527**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	600

Table 1 : Correlation

2. Regression Analysis

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	736.276	9	81.808	320.718	.000 ^b
	Residual	150.497	590	.255		
	Total	886.773	599			

Table 2: ANOVA

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.911 ^a	.830	.828	.50505

Table 3: Model Summary

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.010	.073		-.135	.892
	Awareness and Knowledge	.422	.056	.430	7.592	.000
	Required actions to be taken	-.442	.055	-.464	-8.029	.000
	Entertainment	.128	.025	.135	5.206	.000
	Credibility	.071	.032	.075	2.206	.028
	Demographic values	.020	.036	.021	.558	.577
	Builds confidence	.101	.020	.107	5.111	.000
	Patriotism	.107	.040	.113	2.711	.007
	Love, respect and brotherhood	.627	.039	.665	16.258	.000
	Updates on forthcoming projects and actions	-.045	.021	-.049	-2.118	.035

Table 4: Coefficient

3. Correlation

		Do you think that there is any impact of regulatory advertisement of critical issues consumer's perception?
Time-taking	Pearson Correlation	.742**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	600
Irritating/Annoying	Pearson Correlation	.771**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	600
Creates fear in visiting different places, making friends etc.	Pearson Correlation	.632**

	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	600
High rated advertisements causes impulsive reaction	Pearson Correlation	.507**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	600
Discourages to work physically and use tech savvy products	Pearson Correlation	.677**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	600
Urge of doing unwanted acts/stunts	Pearson Correlation	.688**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	600
Knowledge on unethical actions	Pearson Correlation	.580**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	600
incredibility	Pearson Correlation	.581**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	600

Table 5 : Correlation

4. Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.861 ^a	.742	.738	.62245

Table 6 : Model Summary

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	657.794	8	82.224	212.222	.000 ^b
	Residual	228.979	591	.387		
	Total	886.773	599			

Table 7: ANOVA

.Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.150	.079		1.905	.057
	Time-taking	.219	.032	.230	6.767	.000
	Irritating/Annoying	.368	.033	.381	11.113	.000

Creates fear in visiting different places, making friends etc.	.416	.058	.426	7.235	.000
High rated advertisements causes impulsive reaction	.158	.026	.166	6.009	.000
Discourages to work physically and use tech savvy products	.008	.036	.008	.214	.831
Urge of doing unwanted acts/stunts	.326	.043	.337	7.558	.000
Knowledge on unethical actions	.270	.081	.276	3.329	.001
incredibility	-.792	.101	-.815	-7.847	.000

Table 8 : Coefficient

